

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The role of attitude mediates the effect of brand awareness and brand image on product purchase intention

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of attitude in mediating brand awareness and brand image on purchase intention. The population in this study were consumers who had never used the Carasun brand sunscreen in Denpasar City. The number of samples used in this study were 160 samples. The method used in sample selection is purposive sampling, which is a sampling technique with certain considerations. The analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis based on Partial Least Square (PLS). The results showed that brand awareness and brand image have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, brand awareness and brand image have a positive and significant effect on attitude, attitude has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, and attitude has a role in partially mediating brand awareness and brand image on purchase intention. The results of the study can be concluded that the higher the brand awareness and the creation of a positive brand image in the minds of consumers, the positive consumer attitudes will emerge which encourage making purchases. The higher the brand awareness and the creation of a positive brand image in the minds of consumers, the higher the consumer's purchase intention. The creation of a positive attitude from consumers will create purchase intentions. The higher the brand awareness and the creation of a positive brand image will create a positive attitude from consumers, so that in the end the consumer's purchase intention will increase.

Keywords: Brand Awareness; Brand Image; Attitude; Purchase Intention

1. Introduction

Brand image is one of the factors most remembered by consumers when they want to buy products from certain brands and is one of the important elements that can facilitate the product marketing process within the company (Kurniawan, 2022). Consumer perceptions of brand image play a major role in determining consumer attitudes, although brand characteristics and properties also play an important role, brand reputation remains the most influential factor in influencing customer behavior, despite changes in consumer preferences and information processing processes (Hui and Salman, 2023). Building a strong brand perception in the minds of customers is very important (Mandagi *et al.*, 2022). In developing a brand, brand image plays an important role because it has a reputation and credibility that guides consumers in trying a product or service (Mandagi *et al.*, 2022).

Brand image has an influence on consumer purchase intentions, this is based on studies conducted by Huang *et al.* (2019); Bhakuni *et al.* (2020); Farahan and Lestari (2023); Lukitaningsih *et al.* (2023); Saiddun and Ratnaningrum (2022) this shows that the role of brand image is significant in the decision-making process during purchase, serving as a key factor that positively influences brand selection and determines purchasing decisions. A solid brand image creates strong feelings and confidence in customers, conveying core values that ultimately have a positive impact on purchase intentions. Thus, a positive brand image will indirectly shape consumer attitudes towards the brand. Contrary to

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previous empirical studies, studies conducted by Ramadhan and Santosa (2017); Negarawan (2018) found that brand image has no effect on consumer purchase intention.

Attitude is believed to be one of the factors in influencing a person's intention to make a purchase (Gammama *et al.*, 2022). When a person's attitude towards a particular behavior is perceived as favorable, they are more likely to engage in that behavior. Consumer attitude is a person's expression that is reflected in feelings of liking or disliking an object (Ajzen, 1999). Studies regarding attitudes towards a brand, both positive and negative, play a role in influencing purchase intentions, where this attitude is an important factor in determining the extent to which a person plans to buy the product so that the more positive an individual's attitude towards the product, the more likely they are to buy it (Omar *et al.*, 2023).

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Nadiya and Ishak (2022) found that attitude can be an antecedent in influencing purchase intention. Other research conducted by Singhal and Malik (2018); Chin *et al.* (2018); Mamun *et al.* (2020) also found that attitude towards a product is a very good factor for predicting consumer purchase intentions. In contrast to the research conducted by Trisna and Sefnedi (2018) found that attitude has no influence on purchase intention.

Consumer purchase intention refers to the extent to which consumers are willing to buy a product or service, this is influenced by various factors, such as perceived value, consumer attitudes, trust and opinion dynamics (Chen *et al.* 2018). Examination of these factors helps businesses understand the influence on purchase intentions and increase sales where this study is important theoretically and practically because it helps businesses understand consumer behavior and design effective marketing strategies (Chen *et al.* 2018). Purchase intention is understood as the extent to which consumers are willing to buy a product through an online store, an increase in purchase intention means an increase in purchase opportunities, meaning that if consumers have a positive purchase intention, then positive engagement will drive the purchase (Nguyen *et al.* 2022).

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

The creation of strong brand awareness in the minds of consumers will affect consumer purchase intentions, because in general consumers will tend to buy products that they already know than brands that they do not know. Top of mind is the highest level of awareness in brand awareness, when a brand has succeeded in reaching this level, the brand will minimize existing competitiveness. A number of studies conducted by Mulyaputri (2021); Suciawan (2022); Tan *et al.* (2021); Nafanu (2020); Arta Eliasari and Gde Sukaatmadja (2017) found that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchase intention.

- H1: Brand Awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention

A strong brand image can stimulate consumer interest in returning to buy the product or service in question. By strengthening a positive impression, brand image is not only a determining factor in the initial purchase decision, but also the main driver behind the desire to choose the brand again in subsequent transactions. Research conducted by Bhakuni *et al.* (2020) shows that brand image has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions where a strong brand image evokes strong and confident feelings in customers and conveys core values which in turn positively influence repurchase intentions. This is in line with research conducted by Lukitaningsih *et al.* (2023); Farahan and Lestari (2023); Saiddun and Ratnaningrum (2022); Fikri Anwar *et al.* (2022) state that brand image has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions.

- H2: Brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention

Brand awareness has an important role in determining consumer attitudes, brand awareness is the awareness of potential consumers to recognize and remember that a brand is part of a particular product. The high level of consumer awareness makes a brand always in their minds so that consumers do not hesitate in making purchasing decisions (Arianty and Andira, 2021). Consumers generally prefer to buy brands that they already know to reduce the risk of the

product, so here the role of brand awareness is very important to form a positive attitude of consumers to purchase products (Prayogo *et al.*, 2020). Brand awareness is a measure of the strength of brand existence in the minds of customers, companies with high brand awareness can influence consumer attitudes to make purchases (Khairunisa *et al.*, 2020). Research conducted by Hankho and Cokki (2020); Sukiarti *et al.* (2016) also stated that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes.

- H3: Brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes

Brand image creates a mental framework in the consumer's mind related to a particular brand or product, and consumer attitudes towards the brand are often a direct result of the brand image (Liu *et al.*, 2020). The study conducted by Abin *et al.* (2022) shows that brand image has a strong relationship with attitudes, brand image can also trigger emotional responses in consumers, brands that have a strong and positive image often create a more personal relationship with their consumers so that consumers feel emotionally connected to the brand and will have a positive and loyal attitude towards the brand. Research conducted by Kurniawan (2022) states that brand image has a positive influence on attitudes because brand image is a perception and belief held by consumers which is reflected in the associations embedded in customer memories, which are always remembered the first time they hear the slogan and are embedded in the minds of consumers. Research conducted by Ismitiara *et al.* (2021); Saniatuzzahroh and Trisnawati (2022); Dwitari and Kusdibyo (2019) states that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

- H4: Brand image has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes

Marketing activities using digital technology can build awareness and image of a brand in the eyes of consumers by implementing advertising campaigns, improving the quality of communication strategies, and the main structural elements required for effective implementation (Chunikhina *et al.*, 2023). Research conducted by Wedayanti and Ardani (2020); Ghadani (2022); Gunawan and Sugiharto (2016); Tantra, *et al.* (2022) states that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on brand image, this means that the better the delivery of brand awareness from the company, the better the brand image formed in the minds of consumers. Based on previous empirical studies, the hypothesis of this study can be formulated as follows:

- H5: Brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on brand image

Attitude is a person's positive or negative feelings towards the performance of the target behavior (Ashinze *et al.*, 2021). To influence a consumer's attitude, marketers often use marketing strategies that try to build a positive image, improve product impressions, provide a good customer experience, and communicate with consumers effectively to influence their attitude towards a particular product or service (Amaoko *et al.*, 2020). Nadiya and Ishak's research (2022) found that attitude can be an antecedent in influencing purchase intention. Someone will feel good when they use the right product, that positive view can form a positive attitude and encourage their purchase intention towards purchasing environmentally friendly skin care products. Singhal and Malik (2018); Chin *et al.* (2018); Mamun *et al.* (2020); Adinata and Yasa (2018) also found that attitude towards a product is a very good predictor of consumer purchase intention.

- H6: Attitude has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention

Consumer awareness and trust in brands provide favorable results, consumers tend to have a positive mindset and can lead to a positive attitude towards making purchases (Folia and Yulianti, 2023). Attitude is an important factor influencing consumers to buy products. consumers who have a positive attitude towards a brand will be interested in buying the product. attitude also describes consumer confidence in the various attributes of a brand (Andini and Astuti, 2023). Research conducted by Hanfan (2017) and Pratiwi & Rahanatha (2016) states that attitude can mediate brand awareness on purchase intention.

- H7: Attitude can significantly mediate the effect of brand awareness on purchase intention.

Attitude is the extent to which a person has a favorable or unfavorable evaluation or assessment of a behavior towards a new thing (Nguyen *et al.*, 2017). In order to influence purchase intentions, companies often focus on building and maintaining a positive brand image through various marketing, branding, and brand management strategies, this includes delivering consistent messages, providing a good customer experience, and building long-term relationships with consumers. The more positive the brand image, the more likely consumers are to have purchase intentions for products or services related to that brand (Setiani *et al.*, 2021).

Research conducted by Purwati and Cahyani (2022) states that brand image has an effect on purchase intention. This is in line with research conducted by Sujana and Giantari (2017); Giantari and Dewi (2020); Purwianti (2021) which

shows that brand image affects purchase intention. Based on previous empirical studies, the hypothesis of this study can be formulated as follows:

- H8: Attitude can significantly mediate the effect of brand image on purchase intention.

Figure 1 Research Framework

3. Methods

This research was conducted in Denpasar City. The subjects of this study were sunscreen users who had never used the Carasun brand sunscreen and lived in Denpasar City. The object of this research, namely, measuring consumer attitudes in mediating brand awareness and brand image on consumer purchase intentions in Denpasar City. The population in this study are people who live in Denpasar City who have never used the Carasun brand sunscreen. In this study, the population size is not clearly known.

The sampling technique used in this study is a non-probability sampling method, which is a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample, using a purposive sampling approach. Consideration of determining this sample is for respondents who live in Denpasar and have purchased Carasun sunscreen products. According to Hair *et al.* (2020) the number of representative samples ranges from 100-200 respondents, this study used 160 samples. With the following criteria:

- Domiciled in Denpasar
- Have never bought and used the Carasun brand sunscreen
- Education at least high school / equivalent because
- this education is considered to have good knowledge.
- This survey was only filled out by women because most sunscreen users are women.

This research uses a survey method, to get answers in writing according to the questions the researcher asks. The survey was conducted offline and online. Offline surveys, namely, researchers distributed questionnaires directly to 13 respondents in the field to obtain data. Online surveys were conducted via google form by distributing survey links via the Whatsaap application to 147 respondents in connection with the effectiveness and efficiency of time in this study. This study uses component-based or variant Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), namely Partial Least Square (PLS) for data analysis.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Inner Model

The R-square value is used to determine how much (percentage) the influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable is, the range of the R-square value is 0-1, if the R-square value approaches 0, the weaker the influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable, conversely if it approaches 1, the stronger the influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable.

Table 1 R-Square

	R-Square	R Square Adjusted
Brand Image (Y1)	0.827	0.826
Attitude (Y2)	0.874	0.873
Purchase Intention (Y3)	0.920	0.919

Primary Data, 2024

Based on the data presented in Table 1, it can be explained that the R-square value for the brand image variable is 0.827, which means that this research model is moderate or 82.7 percent of brand image is influenced by brand awareness, the remaining 17.3 percent is influenced by other factors not included in the model. The R-square value for variable Y2 (attitude) is 0.874, which means that this research model is moderate or 87.4 percent of attitudes are influenced by brand awareness and brand image, the remaining 12.6 percent is influenced by other factors not included in the model. The R-square value for variable Y (purchase intention) is 0.920, which means that this research model is moderate or 92.0 percent of purchase intention is influenced by brand awareness, brand image, and attitude, while the remaining 8.0 percent is influenced by other factors not included in the model.

$$Q^2 = 1 - [(1 - R_1^2)(1 - R_2^2)(1 - R_3^2)]$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - [(1 - 0,827)(1 - 0,874)(1 - 0,920)]$$

$$Q^2 = 0,998$$

The Q2 value is in the range of $0 < Q^2 < 1$, where the closer to 1 means the better the model. Based on the calculation results, the Q2 value obtained is 0.998, so it can be concluded that the model has good predictive relevance, thus, it can be explained that 99.8% of the variables are influenced by brand awareness, brand image and attitude variables. Purchase intention is influenced by brand awareness, brand image and attitude while the remaining 0.2 percent is influenced by other factors not included in the model.

4.2. Direct Effect

Testing the direct effect hypothesis using Partial Least Square (PLS) will show five hypotheses. The hypothesis test aims to determine how much influence the exogenous variables have on the endogenous variables. The significance value can be obtained using the bootstrapping technique developed by Geisser and Stone. The statistical test used for hypothesis testing is the t-test. The alternative hypothesis is accepted if the p-value $< \alpha$ 5%. Table 2 shows the direct effect with bootstrapping from the SEMPLS analysis.

Table 2 Direct Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Brand Awareness on Brand Image	0.909	0.911	0.017	52.448	0.000
Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention	0.271	0.285	0.079	3.425	0.001
Brand Image on Purchase Intention	0.279	0.275	0.064	4.374	0.000
Brand Awareness on Attitude	0.428	0.437	0.105	4.096	0.000
Brand Image on Attitude	0.528	0.520	0.105	5.009	0.000
Attitude to Purchase Intention	0.438	0.428	0.066	6.661	0.000

Primary Data, 2024

- The effect of brand awareness on brand image with a large effect value of 0.909 (positive) means that the direction of this test is in accordance with the hypothesis proposed, the t-statistics value of 52.448 and the p-values of 0.000 indicate that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on brand image, so that H1 in this study is accepted.

- The effect of brand awareness on purchase intention with a large effect value of 0.271 (positive) means that the direction of this test is in accordance with the hypothesis proposed, the t-statistics value of 3.425 and the p-values of 0.001 indicate that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, so H2 in this study is accepted.
- The effect of brand image on purchase intention with a large effect value of 0.279 (positive) means that the direction of this test is in accordance with the hypothesis proposed, the t-statistics value of 4.374 and the p-values of 0.000 indicate that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, so H3 in this study is accepted.
- The effect of brand awareness on attitude with a large effect value of 0.428 (positive) means that the direction of this test is in accordance with the hypothesis proposed, the t-statistics value of 4.096 and the p-values of 0.000 indicate that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on attitude, so H4 in this study is accepted.
- The effect of brand image on attitude with a large effect value of 0.528 (positive) means that the direction of this test is in accordance with the hypothesis proposed, the t-statistics value of 5.009 and the p-values of 0.000 indicate that brand image has a positive and significant effect on attitude, so H5 in this study is accepted.
- The effect of attitude on purchase intention with a large effect value of 0.438 (positive) means that the direction of this test is in accordance with the hypothesis proposed, the t-statistics value of 6.661 and the p-values of 0.000 indicate that attitude has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention, so H6 in this study is accepted.

Figure 2 Inner Model

4.3. Indirect Effect

Table 3 Indirect Effect

OriginalSample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation(STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	
Brand Awareness (X1) -> Attitudes (Y2) -> Purchase Intention (Y3)	0.188	0.186	0.048	3.899	0.000
Brand Image (Y1) -> Attitudes (Y2) -> Purchase Intention (Y3)	0.232	0.224	0.061	3.770	0.000

Primary Data, 2024

The examination of mediating variables in this study will be examined regarding the mediating role of attitude variables on the indirect effect of brand awareness and brand image on purchase intention. The examination of indirect effects in this study can be seen in the explanation of the analysis results in Table 3 as follows:

- The p-value for testing the role of attitude in mediating brand awareness on purchase intention is 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. The t statistical value shows 3.899, whose value is greater than 1.96. This data shows that attitude is able to mediate brand awareness on purchase intention.
- The p-value for testing the role of attitude in mediating brand image on purchase intention is 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. The t statistical value shows 3.770 whose value is greater than 1.96. This data shows that attitude is able to mediate brand image on purchase intention.

Mediation testing to determine the indirect effects that occur between variables, the mediation model test is carried out. This measurement in principle is to test and intervention of the mediating variable, whether it is proven to mediate either fully (fully mediated) or partially (partially mediated), or does not act as a mediating variable. The method of testing the mediating variables used in this test is in accordance with the criteria of Hair *et al.* (2014). From the results of the data analysis conducted, the results can be described as follows:

- The value of a is obtained by looking at the significance level of the influence between exogenous variables on endogenous variables. In this study, the exogenous variables are brand awareness and brand image whose significance values are 0.001 and 0.000. This shows the value of a1 and a2 is significant.
- The value of b is obtained by looking at the significance level of the effect of exogenous variables on the mediating variable. In this study, the mediating variable used is attitude, whose significance level value, namely brand awareness on attitude is 0.000, and brand image on attitude is 0.000. This shows that the value of b is significant.
- The value of c is obtained by looking at the significance level of the effect of the mediating variable on the endogenous variable. The significance level of attitude towards purchase intention is 0.000. This means that the value of c is significant.

4.4. Mediate Variables

Hair *et al.* (2014) suggests that there are 4 (four) criteria for testing mediating variables, namely: If a, b, and c are significant but the direct coefficient value $c < b$, then it is said to be partial mediation, if a and b are significant, but c is not significant, then it is said to be perfect mediation (full mediation). After these criteria are met, the next step is to calculate the Variance Accounted For (VAF) with the formula indirect effect divided by the total effect (direct effect plus indirect effect). VAF is a measure of how much the mediating variable is able to absorb the previously significant direct effect of the model without mediation. There are three mediation assessments with this method, namely:

- If the VAF value is greater than 80 percent, it is said to be full mediation.
- If the VAF value is in the range of 20 percent to 80 percent, it is said to be partial mediation.
- If the VAF value is less than 20 percent, it is said that there is no mediating influence.

From this explanation, it is necessary to calculate the value of the direct and indirect effects of each variable.

Table 4 Effect Testing

	OriginalSample (O)	P value	Result
Direct Effect			
X1 -> Y3 (a1)	0.271	0.001	Significant
Y1 -> Y3 (a2)	0.279	0.000	Significant
Indirect Effect			
X1 -> Y2 (b1)	0.428	0.000	Significant
Y2-> Y3 (c1)	0.438	0.000	Significant
Y1 -> Y3 (b2)	0.528	0.000	Significant
Y2 -> Y3(c2)	0.438	0.000	Significant

X1 -> Y3 trough Y2 (b1*c1)	0.188	0.000	Significant
Y1 -> Y3 trough Y2 (b2*c2)	0.232	0.000	Significant
Total Effect			
X1 -> Y3 trough Y2 (a1)+(b1*c1)	0.459		
Y1 -> Y3 trough Y2 (a2)+(b2*c2)	0.510		
For VAF (b*c) : [a+(b*c)]			
VAF1	40.93%		Partial Mediation
VAF2	45.40%		Partial Mediation

Primary Data, 2024

Based on the calculation results, it can be seen that the VAF value for the model of brand awareness influence on purchase intention mediated by attitude is 40.93 percent, while the VAF value for the model of brand image influence on purchase intention mediated by attitude is 45.40 percent. Because the VAF values of the two models are in the range of 20 percent to 80 percent, it can be concluded that these two models are partial mediation

5. Conclusion

Theoretically supports most of the theories of Planned Behavior and Hierarchy of Effects Model that have existed previously. This study is expected to provide empirical contributions regarding the relationship between brand awareness, brand image, attitude, and purchase intention variables for the development of marketing science.

Based on the results of the study which show that brand awareness affects purchase intention, brand image affects purchase intention, brand awareness affects attitude, brand image affects attitude, and attitude is able to mediate between brand awareness and brand image on purchase intention. Based on the results of the study, this study is able to enrich the development of marketing management science and support other empirical studies related to the influence of brand awareness and brand image on purchase intention mediated by attitude.

The results of this study are expected to be a contribution for companies engaged in skin care, especially Carasun, in building good brand awareness and brand image in the community so that top of mind and positive perceptions from the community are created towards the products offered. The first practical implication can be seen from the indicator score that measures the purchase intention variable where consumers are interested in seeking information about Carasun brand sunscreen. Companies are expected to continue to provide information that can be easily accessed by consumers through social media, so that consumers have product knowledge and can grow consumer trust in the products offered. This study also found that consumers are interested in buying Carasun products based on advertisements and reviews that consumers read via the internet, reflected in the highest score obtained on the attitude variable. This shows that companies can continue to educate consumers about products, so that consumers have an idea of the products offered.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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